

Two-Dimensional Moiré Polaronic Electron Crystals

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ABSTRACT. Two-dimensional moiré materials have emerged as the most versatile platform for realizing quantum phases of electrons. Here, we explore the stability origins of correlated states in WSe_2/WS_2 moiré superlattices. We find that ultrafast electronic excitation leads to partial melting of the Mott states on time scales five times longer than predictions from the charge hopping integrals and that the melting rates are thermally activated, with activation energies of 18 ± 3 and 13 ± 2 meV for the one- and two-hole Mott states, respectively, suggesting significant electron-phonon coupling. DFT calculation of the one-hole Mott state confirms polaron formation and yields a hole-polaron binding energy of 16 meV. These findings reveal a close interplay of electron-electron and electron-phonon interactions in stabilizing the polaronic Mott insulators at transition metal dichalcogenide moiré interfaces.

Realizing quantum phases of electrons with high critical temperatures (T_c) has been one of the most important goals in quantum materials research, as exemplified by the longstanding and sometimes contentious quest for high T_c superconductors. Since the discoveries in magic-angle

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twisted bilayer graphene (MATBG) [1,2], moiré interfaces have become rich playgrounds for quantum phases. We focus on transition metal dichalcogenide (TMD) moiré superlattices that host a plethora of correlated charge orders [3–12]. The ordered phases are commonly observed at cryogenic temperatures, but a few exhibits high T_c , e.g., ~ 150 K for Mott states [4,5,8,10,12]. While mechanistic discussions have focused on many-body electron-electron (e-e) interactions, the potential role of electron-phonon (e-ph) interactions has been mostly neglected. In the related phenomena of charge density waves (CDWs) [13], e-e and e-ph interactions play equally important roles. Periodic modulation of electron density is accompanied by periodic lattice distortion in a CDW, as one introduces modulation in the potential landscape to the other. Here we explore if periodic electron density in a moiré superlattice also introduces periodic lattice distortion from e-ph coupling

For electrons excited out of an ordered state, the time scale for melting is dictated by that of the electron hopping integral (t), $\tau_{e-e} \sim \hbar/t$, or the period of the relevant phonon mode, τ_{ph} , when the ordering is dominated by e-e or e-ph interactions, respectively [14]. For TMD moiré superlattices hosting correlated states, the hopping integrals are $t \sim 1-5$ meV [3,15], corresponding to $\tau_{e-e} \sim 660-130$ fs. If e-ph coupling is important, the localization of an electron/hole to a moiré unit cell can be considered as forming a small polaron [16,17]. Deformation of the moiré unit cell likely involves acoustic phonons [16] in momentum range defined by the moiré mini-Brillouin zone, with mean frequencies in the range of $\sim 0.1-1$ THz [18] or time scales of $\sim 10-1$ ps.

Correlated Insulator States and Exciton Sensing

We choose WSe_2/WS_2 heterobilayers with twist angles $\theta = 0 \pm 1^\circ$ and $60 \pm 1^\circ$, where correlated electronic states have been demonstrated with exciton sensing [4,5,8,10]. The moiré lattice constants ($a_M \sim 8$ nm) are the same and band flattening occurs at both twist angles, leading to the similarly observed correlated electronic states. Fig. 1a shows device structure, with an optical image of the 60° device (D1), Fig. 1b, and the reflectance map, Fig. 1c. Under negative (positive) gate bias (V_g), holes (electrons) are injected into the heterojunction and, due to type-II band alignment, reside in the WSe_2 (WS_2) layer [4,5]. We control the moiré lattice filling factor (ν) by V_g and maintain a zero electric field (Methods). Here $\nu < 0$ and $\nu > 0$ correspond to hole and electron doping, respectively. Two additional 0° sample (D2 and D3) are shown in Figs. S1, S2 [19].

The oscillator strength of the sensing exciton is enhanced upon correlated state formation—a result of the accompanying reduction in the effective dielectric constant (ϵ_{eff}) [4,5,8,10]. This is shown for D1 in the photoluminescence (PL) spectrum from interlayer excitons, Fig. 1d, and reflectance spectrum from intralayer excitons, Fig. 1e. Both spectra as functions of V_g identify the charge neutral ($\nu = 0$), one- and two-hole ($\nu = -1, -2$), and one- and two-electron ($\nu = 1, 2$) states [8,12]. Similar results are obtained for the 0° devices (Fig. S1-S2). While the $\nu = -1$ state has been called a Mott [20] or a charge-transfer insulator [21], the $\nu = -2$ state is a Mott insulator of double occupation [22].

Figure 1. WSe₂/WSe₂ device ($\theta = 60^\circ$, D1): structure and characterization. **a** Schematic of the device showing the top (V_t) and bottom (V_b) gates consisting of few-layer graphite (Gr) and hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) encapsulating the WSe₂/WS₂ heterobilayer. **b** Optical image of the sample where the top and bottom gates are labeled, along with outlines showing the Gr electrodes (blue and orange lines corresponding to the top and bottom electrodes, respectively) and the WSe₂/WS₂ overlap region (white line). **c** Steady-state reflectance contrast mapping with the white line highlighting the WSe₂/WS₂ overlap region. $\Delta R = R - R_0$; R is the reflectance from the sample in the bilayer region and R_0 is reflectance from the sample stack without the bilayer. **d** Gated ($V_g = V_t = V_b$) steady-state photoluminescence spectrum (with intensity shown on a logarithmic scale). **e** Gated ($V_g = V_t = V_b$) steady-state reflectance spectrum of the lowest energy moiré exciton of WSe₂. All data collected at 11 K.

We apply time-resolved reflectance spectroscopy and focus on the correlated hole states, because sensing from the WSe₂ moiré exciton is most sensitive to holes residing in the same layer. A correlated hole Mott state can be represented by gap opening near the top of the valence band, resulting in a lower Hubbard band (LHB, with holes) and an upper Hubbard band (UHB, without

holes). We choose a pump photon energy (1.55 eV) below the optical gaps of WSe₂ and WS₂ to avoid long-lived interlayer excitons [23]. At this photon energy, a hole in the LHB can be excited deep into the valence band; the excited hole cools on ultrafast time scales to reach the UHB, Fig. 2a. The e-h pair across the Hubbard gap, Fig. 2b, is usually called a holon-doublon pair [13,14]. The subsequent disordering may lead to partial gap closing, Fig. 2c, with accompanying increase in ϵ_{eff} . Figs. 2d-f show 2D plots of transient reflectance as a function V_g at selected delays from the 60° device; the signal is $\Delta R/R$, where ΔR is the pump-induced reflectance change and R is the reflectance without pump. The peaks in $\Delta R/R$ only appear around V_g values commensurate with $\nu = -1$ and -2 and vary with Δt . Similar results are obtained for the 0° samples (Fig. S1-S2).

Fig. 2. Pump-probe of a hole Mott state in hole-doped WSe₂/WS₂. **a.** Excitation of a hole (green) from the lower Hubbard band (LHB) to a deep valence state, with subsequent cooling of the photo-excited hole (green sphere) to the upper Hubbard band (UHB). The hole energy scale is opposite to that of an electron scale. **b.** Real space representation of the holon-doublon pair for the hole (green spheres) Mott state, with corresponding state representation on the top of each cartoon; **c.** Partial melting (disordering) and gap closing from holon-doublon excitation. **d-f** Transient reflectance spectra plotted as a function of probe energy (covering the first moiré exciton of WSe₂) versus gate voltage ($V_g = V_t = V_b$) at $\Delta t = 2, 8, 50$ ps in d-f, respectively. Features specific to the $\nu = -1, -2$ states can be observed and seen to evolve as a function of Δt . Here, $\Delta R/R$ is the transient reflectance signal calculated from pump-on and -off spectra. The pump fluence employed for the transient measurements was 57 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. All spectra collected at 11 K.

Melting Dynamics of the Correlated States

Figure 3. Temperature-dependent temporal response of correlated states. **a-c** Transient reflectance traces of the $\nu = 0, -1, -2$ states, respectively, averaged over a ~ 0.01 eV probe energy range about the maximum of the lowest energy moiré band of WSe_2 . The coherent artifact resulting from pump-probe overlap can be seen at $\Delta t = 0$ ps. The time traces have been offset for clarity. The colors corresponding to each temperature are labeled in panel a and are consistent throughout the figure. The employed pump fluence was $14 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. All data shown is for sample D1.

Fig. 3 contains pump-probe data for the $\nu = 0, -1,$ and -2 states of the 60° sample. These measurements are carried out in a pump fluence regime where two photon absorption does not contribute (see Fig. S3 and Fig. S4). The only observed dynamics for $\nu = 0$ (Fig. 3a) correspond to low frequency phonons, which appear as delayed and periodic modulations in $\Delta R/R$ on an otherwise flat background (see Figs. S5, S6). For the $\nu = -1, -2$ states, in addition to phonons, we observe a decrease in overall $\Delta R/R$ in picoseconds, followed by recovery at longer times. The decrease in $\Delta R/R$ is attributed to an increase in ϵ_{eff} from disordering, referred to as “melting”. We melting time (τ_m) from single exponential fits to the initial decays in $\Delta R/R$ in Fig. 3b, 3c (see Fig. S5 for details): $\tau_m = 3.2 \pm 0.2$ ps ($\nu = -1$) and 3.4 ± 0.1 ps ($\nu = -2$) at $T \leq 40$ K. These τ_m values are at least five times longer than those predicted from the charge hopping integrals, but are in the range

estimated from acoustic phonons. The pump-induced changes to ϵ_{eff} are not resolved for fractional filling factors, Fig. S7.

For either $\nu = -1$ or -2 , τ_m remains constant until ~ 40 K, above which it decays monotonically, Fig. 4a. There are two regions: 1) at $T \leq 40$ K, temperature independence is expected from e-e interaction; 2) at $T > 40$ K, e-ph interactions become important and melting is thermally activated. We plot melting rates, $k_m = 1/\tau_m$, with temperature, Fig. 4b-c for $\nu = -1, -2$, respectively, and fit the data to the Arrhenius equation, $k_m \propto \exp[-E_a/k_B T]$, where E_a is the activation energy and k_B the Boltzmann constant. A constant offset is included to account for the temperature-independent contribution. These fits yield $E_a = 18 \pm 3$ meV and 13 ± 2 meV for the $\nu = -1$ and -2 , respectively.

Figure 4. Polaronic nature of correlated states. **a** Temperature-dependent melting time (τ_m) of the $\nu = -1, -2$ states resulting from the pump pulse. **b, c** Melting rates, k_m , corresponding to panel **a**. The dashed lines are fits to the Arrhenius equation to extract thermal activation energies for $\nu = -1, -2$ of $E_a = 18 \pm 3$ meV and 13 ± 2 meV, respectively. Constant offsets account for non-zero melting rates at lower temperatures. **d** Temperature-dependent transient reflectance for the $\nu = 0, -1, -2$ states (shown in gray, green, purple, respectively). For each data point, the corresponding transient reflectance spectra was averaged over a ~ 0.01 eV probe energy range about the maximum of the lowest energy WSe₂ moiré exciton peak and averaged over a pump-probe delay of $\Delta t = 4-8$ ps. All error bars indicate 99% confidence intervals. All data shown is for sample D1.

The activation energies obtained from the melting rates are on the order of thermal dissociation energies estimated from T_c . While intensity of the sensing exciton in static reflectance (Fig. S8) may be used as a proxy to the order parameter in the Mott states [4,8], the presence of background signal makes analysis difficult. We use transient reflectance instead for $\nu = -1$ (green) and -2 (purple), with $\nu = 0$ (black) as control, Fig. 4d. The correlated states are still observed at ~ 150 K and ~ 100 K for $\nu = -1, -2$, respectively, providing lower bounds for T_c . These give $k_b T_c \sim 13$ meV and ~ 9 meV for $\nu = -1$ and -2 , respectively; they are $\sim 70\%$ of the E_a values.

The temperature-dependent measurements are also repeated on a second 0° sample (D2) (Fig. S9). We obtain $\tau_m = 3.4 \pm 0.2$ ps for $\nu = -1$ at $T = 8$ K. The temperature dependence in τ_m at $T > 40$

K gives $E_a = 19 \pm 3$ meV and that of $\Delta R/R$ signal gives $T_c \sim 150$ K for the $\nu = -1$ state. These results are in excellent agreement with those measured in the 60° sample (D1) and confirm that the similar thermal dissociation temperatures observed for the correlated states in the 0° and 60° samples share the same physical origin. The differences in the moiré potential trap depth at 0° and 60° [24] do not seem to impact the melting/reordering dynamics of the Mott states. While we focus on melting, the recovery dynamics (Fig. S10) are more complex. The recovery of the $\nu = -1$ state is essentially temperature-independent, suggesting that e-e scattering limits the reformation of the Mott state [25]. The recovery of the $\nu = -2$ state, however, shows significant temperature dependence, pointing to the role of e-ph interactions. These processes deserve further investigations.

Polaronic Nature of the Correlated Mott Insulators

The melting rates and, more importantly, their thermal activations suggest electron-phonon coupling in the $\nu = -1$ and -2 Mott states. In a correlated insulator, the residence time of each electron (hole) in a moiré unit cell is much longer than that of an uncorrelated electron, due to inhibition of charge hopping and much reduced kinetic energy in the former. The long residence time can lead to local polarization of the lattice to form a small polaron with the signature thermal activation [16]. The correlated insulator states are likely small polaron lattices. Here we use “small” to describe the size of the polaron with respect to the moiré length scale.

To corroborate polaron formation, we carry out density functional theory (DFT) calculations based on the PBE exchange-correlation functional on a $\theta = 0^\circ$ WSe_2/WS_2 bilayer (Methods, Fig. S11). We first relax the structure of the neutral system, followed by additional structural relaxation upon introducing a positive charge into the moiré unit cell ($\nu = -1$). Charge localization is evident from the spatial distribution of geometrical rearrangement which occurs upon injection of a positive charge into each unit cell,

Figure 5. *Ab initio* charge-induced lattice distortion. Structural reorganization averaged over the atomic positions on each lattice point upon injection of a positive charge in an aligned WS_2/WSe_2 bilayer. The color scale represents the degree of distortion at each lattice position, $\langle \mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{r}_0 \rangle$.

Fig. 5. The periodic electron density in the moiré superlattice introduces periodic lattice distortion, which is 90% perpendicular to the bilayer plane. We calculate a total reorganization energy of 16

meV; this can be taken as the polaron binding energy. This calculation is at the single-hole level, without the explicit inclusion of many-body correlation in the Hubbard Hamiltonian [3]. The resulting polaron binding energy agrees surprisingly well with experimental activation energies; although PBE-DFT is not expected to quantitatively account for e-ph coupling, it correctly describes the pattern of structural reorganization [26]. The disordering or melting of an ordered hole lattice requires hole hopping among moiré unit cells. In the small polaron picture, charge hopping requires thermal activation of phonons to overcome the polaron binding energy and release the hole from the trap. Thus, the thermal activation energy is related to the polaron binding energy [16,17,27].

Concluding Comments

The results presented here reveal the polaronic nature of correlated insulator states in the WSe_2/WS_2 moiré system. Our findings challenge the conventional many-body electron Hamiltonian and suggest the necessity of including e-ph coupling in some cases. In 2D materials, Kang et al. provided experimental evidence for Holstein “small” polaron in electron doped MoS_2 from intervalley coupling by zone-boundary longitudinal acoustic phonons [28]. Sio and Giustino reported polaron formation in h-BN; these authors suggested that Fröhlich “large” polaron formation from long-range Coulomb interaction is insignificant in 2D TMDs [29]. Recent theoretical work has also begun to explore e-ph coupling [30–32] in MATBG. The small polaron lattice reported here for Mott states in the TMD moiré system is similar to a CDW state and e-ph interactions may be partially responsible for thermal stability.

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